

HESANDA – MONASH NODE

Master guidelines. November 2023

Abstract

Health Data Australia (HDA) contains descriptions of health datasets, provided by the data owners and stored elsewhere. To get access to the data, researchers submit a request to the owner, who will review and determine whether access can be granted.

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Health Data Australia

Overview of Health Data Australia

Health Data Australia (HDA) helps researchers discover and access health data. They do not store the data itself but provide descriptions of the data from their data publishing partners. Using HDA, researchers can search these descriptions, find data of use to do their research, then request access to it. The request will be sent to the owner of the data to review. Data owners receive email notifications about new data requests and can then log into the HDA Data Request platform to review the request and determine whether access can be granted and then respond to the researcher requesting access. If the request is approved, the owner arranges for the researcher to be given access to the data.

The dataset descriptions ('metadata') contained on HDA help researchers understand the kinds of data that exist and assess whether a dataset may be of value to their research, without the need to actually access the data. In addition to metadata, data owners provide other documentation describing the data they hold, such as study protocols and data dictionaries.

Using HDA, researchers can search for data, save their searches, submit and manage data requests.

HeSANDAs

The information on Health Data Australia was provided by the HeSANDAs network. HeSANDAs is a network of 72 health research organisations working collaboratively as nine 'nodes' to give researchers better access to health data. For more information about HeSANDAs, see [here](#). Health Data Australia launched in July 2023. Over the next five years, it will be expanded to incorporate a wider array of data collections from different health research studies, as well as government and health service data. [Here](#) is the link to the Platform.

The HeSANDAs Network

There are 9 HeSANDAs nodes that represent 72 health research organisations across Australia

Melbourne Academic Centre for Health (MACH) Clinical Trials Consortium Node <i>Administered by:</i> The University of Melbourne	Queensland Node <i>Administered by:</i> Health Translation Queensland
Mental Health Node <i>Administered by:</i> Deakin University	South Australia Node <i>Administered by:</i> South Australian Health and Medical Research Institute (SAHMRI)
Monash and Partners Node <i>Administered by:</i> Monash University	Sydney Health Partners Node <i>Administered by:</i> NHMRC Clinical Trials Centre at The University of Sydney
National Cancer Cooperative Trials Groups Node <i>Administered by:</i> Australasian Leukaemia and Lymphoma Group (ALLG)	West Australian Node <i>Administered by:</i> Curtin University
Northern Australia Node <i>Administered by:</i> Menzies School of Health Research	

Logos: Monash Partners, MONASH University, Australian Research Data Commons

Figure 1. The HeSANDAs network

How to find Data in HeSANDA

How to search in HeSANDA

This guide will walk you through various search techniques and features to enhance your search experience. The search platform is hosted on the Health Data Australia platform (HAD). Here is the link: [HDA](#)

How to conduct a keyword search

Conducting a keyword-based search in HDA allows you to find relevant health datasets based on your specific search terms. This user guide explains the steps to conduct a search in HDA and provides additional information about how to refine your search.

Conduct a Search

The Search Bar is prominently displayed at the top of every page in HDA (refer to Fig 1.1). To initiate a search, simply enter your search terms into the Search Bar at the top of the page and click the 'Search' button. This will execute the search and take you to a page with the corresponding search results, where you can further refine your search.

Fig 1.1 The search bar in Health Data Australia

Narrow Down Your Search

To narrow down your search to a specific field, use the dropdown menu located on the left-hand side of the Search Bar (refer to Fig 1.2). The available search fields include:

- Dataset Title: Search terms will be matched against the title of each health dataset
- Dataset Description: Search terms will be matched against the description of each health dataset
- Dataset Identifier: Search terms will be matched against the assigned identifier of each health dataset
- Study Identifier: Search terms will be matched against the assigned identifier of the study related to the health dataset

Fig 1.2 The dropdown menu

Search for Identifiers

You have the option to search for health datasets using two types of identifiers: Dataset identifier and study identifier. In the current HDA instance, all datasets are assigned a DOI identifier, while studies have an ANZCTR identifier consisting of a 14-digit number with an "ACTRN" prefix, e.g. ACTRN12610000000000.

When searching for a doi, please enter the suffix value after "<https://doi.org/>". For instance, if the complete DOI of the dataset is "<https://doi.org/10.00000/ABCD-1234>", please search using the value "10.00000/ABCD-1234".

To assist your search when you don't have the complete identifier, HDA integrates a wildcard search feature which allows you to directly search for a segment of a complete identifier. For example, entering "0.00000/ABCD-1234" or "BCD-123" in the search field when conducting an identifier search will produce the same search results as entering "10.00000/ABCD-1234".

Search with Exact Phrases

If you want to search for an exact phrase, enclose the phrase in quotes " ". For instance, to search for datasets related to cancer, enter "cancer" into the Search Bar.

Understand your search results

Search result page overview

After conducting a keyword-based search on your selected fields, the portal will redirect you to a search result page which returns records that match the input. All the search results are sorted by 'Relevance', which is determined by a complex algorithm that considers how closely a record matches the entered and selected parameters.

In addition to the dataset itself, the search result page in HDA will display other related information to help you better understand and evaluate the dataset. This includes the name of the publisher who created and provided the dataset, as well as the title of the related study that's been referenced by the dataset. The "search result components" section below provides an example of a returned search result.

Search Result Components

Fig 2.1 An example of a returned health dataset

- Dataset Title - The title of each health dataset returned on the search result page
- Dataset Description - The description of each health dataset returned on the search result page
- Study Title - In Health Data Australia, every dataset is associated with a related study, which provides additional information and increases the metadata richness level. The study title is displayed on the search result page as supportive information to help you better understand the dataset. At this stage, all the studies are retrieved from the Australian New Zealand Clinical Trials Registry (ANZCTR). Some of their metadata fields are used as search parameters to help narrowing down the search results
- Publisher - The organisation which created and provided the health dataset

Pagination

Fig 2.2 Pagination for the search results

- The search result page displays a default of 10 records per page
- If there are more than 10 records matching your search criteria, subsequent pages will be available
- You can navigate between pages using the pagination links displayed at the top and bottom of the search results

How to use faceted search

Once you have executed a search in Health Data Australia (HDA) and arrived at the Search Results page, you can further refine and narrow down your search results using the faceted search feature. The faceted search feature in HDA provides a list of available parameters that will be updated dynamically based on your every selection. This user guide explains how to make use of the faceted search to apply additional filters and modify your search results.

Current Search [Data](#)

Current Selection
Viewing all documents!

Subjects

- Chemotherapy (22)
- Cancer therapy (excl. chemotherapy and radiation therapy) (15)
- FOS: Medical and health sciences (4)
- Infant and child health (4)
- Radiation Therapy (4)
- [show more](#)

Publishers

- Australasian Leukaemia and Lymphoma Group (ALLG) (32)
- University of Melbourne (8)
- Breast Cancer Trials (BCT) (6)
- The University of Sydney (6)
- South Australian Health and Medical Research Institute (SAHMRI) (5)
- [show more](#)

ANZCTR Condition Codes

- Cancer (45)
- Leukaemia - Acute leukaemia (13)
- Mental Health (9)
- Leukaemia - Chronic leukaemia (8)
- Breast (7)
- [show more](#)

ANZCTR Conditions

- Multiple Myeloma (3)
- Anxiety (2)
- Body image dissatisfaction (2)
- Depression (2)
- Eating disorders (2)
- [show more](#)

Study Types

- Interventional (76)
- Observational (1)

Fig 3.1 The faceted search panel

On the left-hand side of the Search Results page, you will find the faceted search panel, which allows you to apply filters to narrow down your search results.

Note

Only the top 5 filter entries are initially displayed in each section. If you wish to view additional filters, click the "show more" link. This action will expand the list to show all available filters. To minimise the list and display only the top 5 entries again, click the "show less" link.

Select Filter(s)

- Review the available filters in the faceted search panel. The number behind each entry represents the number of datasets that will be returned after applying this search condition. In each section, the filters are sorted based on the dataset counts
- Click on the desired filter entry to add it to your search criteria
- As you select filters, both the search results and the faceted search panel will be dynamically updated to reflect your selections. For example, if you choose "Cancer" as the subject in your search, the faceted search will update and display entries that match the "Cancer" subject exclusively

Current Search Data

Current Selection
 ✖ Subjects: Cancer

Subjects

- Cancer (2)
- Complications of newborn (1)
- chemotherapy (1)

Publishers

- HeSANDA University TEST Institute (1)
- Thoracic Oncology Group Australasia (TOGA) (1)

ANZCTR Condition Codes

- Cancer (2)
- Anaesthesiology (1)
- Anxiety (1)
- Any cancer (1)
- Epilepsy (1)
- show more

ANZCTR Conditions

- Advanced non-small cell lung cancer (1)
- Anxiety (1)
- Any recognized condition for which medicinal cannabis could be prescribed for (1)
- Autism (1)
- Chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting (1)
- show more

Study Types

- Interventional (1)
- Observational (1)

Fig 3.2 The available filter options after selecting "Cancer" from the subject list

Remove Filter(s)

- If you need to remove an existing filter selection, locate the entry in the "Current Selection" section of the faceted search panel
- Click on the entry to remove the corresponding filter and update the search results accordingly
- To remove all the applied filters at one time, simply click the "Clear Search" button on top of the "Current Search" panel

Fig 3.3 Clear Search

Related study in HeSANDA (all)

About Related Study

In the context of health research, datasets are closely related to the research or study and serve as a valuable source of information. Hence in HDA, every health dataset is related to a study. Currently, the available study type primarily revolves around clinical trials, sourced from [Australian New](#)

[Zealand Clinical Trials Registry \(ANZCTR\)](#). This section provides insights into the context of the study associated with the dataset. The metadata fields pertaining to the study are grouped into different tabs, ensuring easy navigation and access to specific information of your interest. Certain fields within the tabs are also faceted, allowing you to click on these fields and explore related datasets that share the same attribute.

Related Study

Description	Conditions	Detail
<p>A Single Arm Phase II Study of the Efficacy of Tamoxifen in Triple Negative (oestrogen receptor alpha negative, progesterone receptor negative, HER-2 negative) but Oestrogen Receptor Beta Positive Metastatic Breast Cancer</p> <p>Brief Summary This study looks at the effectiveness of the drug tamoxifen in treating breast cancer which is classified as triple negative (oestrogen receptor alpha negative, progesterone receptor negative, HER-2 negative) and oestrogen receptor beta positive, where the cancer has spread to distant sites (metastases). Who is it for? You can join this study if you are a woman with triple negative metastatic breast cancer that is oestrogen receptor beta positive and chemotherapy and/or radiotherapy is currently not considered appropriate. Prior to entering the study, a sample of metastatic tumour must be tested and confirmed to be oestrogen receptor beta positive. Trial details Some breast cancer cells contain receptors which the female hormone oestrogen binds to, causing the cancer to grow. The study aims to find out whether tamoxifen may be useful for treating metastatic breast cancer that contains the oestrogen beta receptor. Tamoxifen is an anti-oestrogen drug which is frequently used to treat breast cancers that contain the oestrogen alpha receptor but has not been used specifically to treat breast cancers that contain the oestrogen beta receptor. Participants will all receive one oral tablet (20mg) of tamoxifen daily, unless they suffer unacceptable side effects, or their breast cancer progresses.</p>		

Fig 4.1 An example of the Related Study section

Related Study

Description	Conditions	Detail
<p>Conditions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Triple Negative Metastatic Breast Cancer <p>Condition Codes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Breast Cancer <p>Intervention Code</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Treatment: Drugs 		

Fig 4.2 An example of the faceted search fields in the second tab

Save a Search

In order to save a search, you need to set up an account. The next section of this document describes how to do this.

The "Save Search"/"Log in to Save" button is located on top of the "Current Search" panel next to the "Clear Search" button. If you haven't logged in yet, clicking the button will redirect you to the Keycloak authentication page. You can login to the HDA portal following the step-by-step guide documented in [How to Login Using Australian Access Federation \(AAF\)](#) or refer to the next section of this document.

After logging in to HDA, the text on the button will automatically convert to "Save Search".

Fig 4.1 Save Search

By clicking this button, a dialog box will pop out on the screen, prompting you to enter a title for the saved search and save it as one entry on your MyHDA user profile page. You can enter a descriptive and meaningful name that helps you identify the search criteria, then click "Save Search".

Fig 4.2 Assign a title to the saved search

To review, refresh, or delete your saved searches, simply navigate to your MyHDA page and check the "My Saved Search" section. For more information, see:

<https://ardc-datarequest.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/HDA/pages/96862243/MyHDA#My-Saved-Searches>

How to Login Using Australian Access Federation (AAF)

This section provides a step-by-step guide on accessing the Health Data Australia portal by logging in with valid AAF credentials.

What is AAF?

The Australian Access Federation (AAF) is an authentication and authorisation service that allows individuals to securely access online resources and services provided by participating organisations in Australia. It streamlines the access process by providing a unified set of login credentials. By using AAF, you can log in to the Health Data Australia portal without the need for creating separate credentials.

For more information about AAF, see: <https://aaf.edu/au>

About obtaining an AAF account, please refer to: [How to obtain an AAF account](#), or see the next section.

Why log in to HDA?

While you can browse metadata and conduct searches in the Health Data Australia (HDA) portal without logging in, there are several key functionalities that are only available to users with an account. By logging in to HDA, you will obtain a MyHDA user profile page and gain access to the following functionalities:

- Save a search query.
- Save a health dataset.
- Request access to a health dataset and track the process.

For more information, see: [MyHDA](#), or the following section

Steps to log in using AAF

Step 1: Navigate to the portal and locate the Login button

On every page in the HDA portal, the "LOG IN" button is located at the top-right corner of the header. Click on it to proceed to the Keycloak authentication page.

Welcome to Health Data Australia

Fig 1.1 The home page with the LOG IN button on the top

After being navigated to the Keycloak authentication page, click the button "AAF Login". You will be redirected to the AAF Central login page with a list of organisations.

Step 2: Select your organisation

On the AAF Central login page, you will see a list of organisations that are part of the AAF network. Find and select the organisation that you're affiliated with from the list.

This could be your university, research institution, or any other participating organisation. You can also search for your organisation using the provided search bar.

Login to AAF Central

AAF central provides authentication and identity bridging between disparate authentication protocols such as SAML IdP to OpenID Connect RP.

Please select your organisation below, you will be redirected to complete the login process.

Search for your organisation

- AAF Virtual Home
- Actors Centre Australia
- AIMS

Continue to your organisation

Remember my organisation

Australian Access Federation
Test Federation

[Current AAF status](#)
[Contact AAF support](#)

Fig 1.2 The AAF Central Login page

Step 3: Enter your credentials and authenticate with your organisation

After selecting your organisation, you will be redirected to your organisation's login page.

On the login page, you can enter your AAF login credentials, which usually consist of your organisational username and password. If you are unsure about your login credentials, contact your organisation's IT support or helpdesk for assistance.

Once you have entered your login credentials, click on the "Login" or "Authenticate" button to proceed. AAF will communicate with your organization's identity provider to verify your credentials and authenticate your access.

Step 4: Access the HDA portal

After successfully logging in and granting any necessary permissions, you will be redirected back to the HDA portal. You will notice that the items on the top-right menu has been updated to the one below:

Welcome to Health Data Australia

Fig 1.3 The home page after you successfully logged in

Now you should have full access to MyHDA and the full list of functionalities provided by HDA.

MyHDA – HeSANDA

About MyHDA

After [logging in to Health Data Australia \(HDA\) using your AAF credentials](#), you'll gain access to your MyHDA user profile page and unlock the full functionalities of HDA. MyHDA comprises four sections:

- My saved searches
 - Allows you to organise, review and refresh your saved search queries.
- My saved records
 - A centralised section to view the datasets that you bookmarked before.
- My saved requests
 - Allows you to resume editing your unfinished and unsubmitted data requests. Once you started filling in an Express of Interest (EOI) form, you can save it at anytime and come back to resume editing it in the "My saved requests" table.
- My submitted requests
 - Allows you to check the status of the submitted data requests, and take actions accordingly.

Each is designed to provide convenient access and simple management of your saved datasets, searches, and data access requests.

The detailed features and available functionalities will be introduced in each tab accordingly.

The example below shows a sample MyHDA page for a user:

The screenshot displays the 'My HDA' user interface. It features a header with the user's name 'HDA Test User' and a 'Logout' button. Below the header are four main sections, each with a table of data and action buttons. A legend on the right side of the page maps numbers 1 through 5 to these sections: 1. User Profile & Logout, 2. My Saved Searches, 3. My Saved Records, 4. My Saved Data Requests, and 5. My Submitted Data Requests.

MY SAVED SEARCHES		Action
Saved Searches		Refresh Delete
Leukemia - Chronic Neutrophils	First saved 2023-06-27 15:02:22 with 8 data sets found	
Mental Health	First saved 2023-06-27 15:21:45 with 8 data sets found	Refresh Delete

MY SAVED RECORDS		Action
Saved Records		View Delete
Randomised trial of letrozole plus usual care versus usual care without letrozole to prevent new breast cancer events in postmenopausal women who have completed a minimum of 4 years of adjuvant endocrine therapy for early, hormone responsive breast cancer more than 1 year previous, and who are disease-free at trial entry (ANZ 0501 LATER)		

MY SAVED DATA REQUESTS		Action
Saved Data Requests		Resume Delete
The CSC Intervention: A comprehensive universal internet-based intervention to prevent anxiety, depression, substance use, and related harms in Australian adolescents aged 13 to 18 years.		
Last saved 2023-06-27 09:06:02		

MY SUBMITTED DATA REQUESTS		Action
Status	Submitted Data Requests	Update Withdraw
Withdrawn	A Multicentre Phase 3 Trial Comparing Eotuzumab-Cyclophosphamide, Tuzozumab-Cyclophosphamide (E-CIT) with Cyclophosphamide, Trastuzumab, Docetaxel (CTD) for the Treatment of Relapsed and/or Refractory Multiple Myeloma (RRMM) (RRMM)	
	Submitted 2023-06-09 11:31:05	
Data Released	A Phase II Pilot Study of Giv'ec (matinib mesylate formerly known as ST1571) Combined with Induction Chemotherapy in Blast-Phase Chronic Myeloid Leukemia and Philadelphia Chromosome-Positive Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia, to evaluate safety and improve remission rate. (CMALL21)	
	Submitted 2023-06-13 09:44:41	
Submitted	Symptom monitoring With Feedback trial (SWIFT) dataset	
	Submitted 2023-06-14 09:50:37	

- 1 User Profile & Logout
- 2 My Saved Searches
- 3 My Saved Records
- 4 My Saved Data Requests
- 5 My Submitted Data Requests

Fig 1.1 A sample MyHDA page

My Saved Searches

Overview

Both simple keyword searches and complicated search queries can be saved via the "Save Search" button on the search result page. Once the search has been named and saved, you can find the entry in the "My Saved Searches" table along with relevant information. Each entry displays the search name, timestamp, and the number of results returned when the search was initially saved. You can check all the returned records based on the search query, refresh to see the latest results, and delete the saved search if it's no longer needed.

For instructions on how to save a search, see: [Search In HDA](#)

View the Search Results

To view the results that are returned from this search query, simply click the name of the saved search. This action will direct you to a search result page where you can explore all the health datasets that match the search conditions.

Delete the Saved Search

To delete any saved search, simply click the "Delete" button on the same row. A confirmation pop-up window will appear to ensure you want to proceed with the deletion:

Fig 2.1 The confirmation pop-up window

Click "Yes" and wait for the delete operation to finish. Once the pop-out window disappears from the screen, you'll find your previously saved search has been successfully deleted.

Refresh the Saved Search

Refreshing a saved search allows you to check if there are any new health datasets that match the saved search criteria. To refresh a saved search, simply click the "Refresh" button on the same row.

You'll find that an additional caption with the date of the refresh and the number of results has been added under the caption for when it was first saved.

MY SAVED SEARCHES	
Saved Searches	Action
Leukaemia - Chronic leukaemia <i>First saved 2023-06-27 11:15:32 with 8 data sets found.</i>	Refresh Delete
Mental Health <i>First saved 2023-06-27 11:21:46 with 8 data sets found.</i> <i>Last refreshed 2023-06-27 11:28:39 with 8 data sets found.</i>	Refresh Delete

Fig 2.2 An example of the refreshing timestamp and number of datasets found

If you have refreshed this saved search previously, clicking "Refresh" will update this line of caption without adding any new lines.

My Saved Records

How to Save a Record

"My Saved Records" allows you to bookmark any health dataset that you're interested in and would like to come back to later. To save a record, simply click the "Save to MyHDA" button on the record view page.

Fig 3.1 The "Save to MyHDA" button

After this operation, you will find that the text on the button is updated to "Saved to MyHDA", indicating that this record has been successfully saved.

Fig 3.2 The "Saved to MyHDA" button

You will find the corresponding entry in the "My Saved Records" table with 2 action buttons in the same row: View and Delete.

MY SAVED RECORDS	
Saved Records	Action
Randomised trial of letrozole plus usual care versus usual care without letrozole to prevent new breast cancer events in postmenopausal women who have completed a minimum of 4 years of adjuvant endocrine therapy for early, hormone responsive breast cancer more than 1 year previous, and who are disease-free at trial entry (ANZ 0501 LATER)	View Delete
The Fenofibrate And Microvascular Events in Type 1 diabetes Eye (FAME 1 EYE) dataset	View Delete

Fig 3.3 The action buttons

How to View a Saved Record

To view any record that you previously saved, simply click the "View" button, and you'll be redirected to the record view page of this health dataset.

How to Delete a Saved Record

To delete any saved record that you no longer want to keep, simply click the "Delete" button. A confirmation pop-up window will appear to ensure you want to proceed with the deletion:

Fig 3.4 The confirmation pop-up window

Click "Yes" and wait for the delete operation to finish. Once the pop-out window disappears from the screen, you'll find your previously saved search has been successfully deleted.

My Saved Data Requests

How to Edit a Saved Data Access Request

As mentioned in [How to Request Access to a Health Dataset](#), unfinished data access requests can be saved in the "My saved data requests" section. You'll find that the last saved timestamp is also captured below the dataset title.

To resume editing the EOI form, simply click the "Resume" button. You'll be redirected to the unfinished EOI form with all the saved changes.

Throughout the editing process, you can save and resume editing the EOI form as many times as needed. Once you submit the request, it will be moved to the "My submitted data requests" section.

MY SAVED DATA REQUESTS	
Saved Data Requests	Action
<p>The CSC intervention: A comprehensive universal internet-based intervention to prevent anxiety, depression, substance use, and related harms in Australian adolescents aged 13 to 16 years.</p> <p><i>Last saved 2023-06-27 09:06:02</i></p>	<p>Resume Delete</p>

Fig 4.1 My saved data requests

How To Delete a Saved Data Access Request

To delete any saved requests that you no longer want to process, simply click the "Delete" button. A confirmation pop-up window will appear to ensure you want to proceed with the deletion:

Fig 4.2 The confirmation pop-up window

Click "Yes" and wait for the delete operation to finish. Once the pop-out window disappears from the screen, you'll find your previously saved request has been successfully deleted.

The differences between "my saved data requests" and "my submitted data requests":

"My Saved Data Requests" section stores only the data access requests that have not been submitted, whereas "My Submitted Data Requests" section contains the requests that have been submitted. If the "Update" option is available for a submitted data request, you can make edits and save changes to the previously submitted EOI form. However, the saved EOI form will not create a new entry in "My Saved Data Requests". To resume editing a previously submitted request, simply click "Update" again.

My Submitted Data Requests

The "my submitted data requests" table consists of 3 columns: Status, Submitted Data Requests, and Action. The Status column represents the current status of the request, and the action buttons will appear in the Action column if available. All the request statuses and corresponding actions are listed in the table below:

Status	Actions Available
Submitted	Update Withdrawn
Review In Progress	NA
Modifications Requested	Update Withdrawn
In-principle Approval	NA

Denied/Discontinued/Withdrawn/Data Released	NA
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If your request has recently been submitted and hasn't undergone the review process, you have the option to update the EOI form if any information was missing or withdraw the request. However, once the request is under review or has received in-principle approval, you will not be able to make any changes to the EOI form.

In the event that the data custodian requests modifications, you will also have the available options to either update the EOI form accordingly or withdraw the request if you choose not to proceed with the required modifications.

When the status of a request is marked as Denied, Discontinued, Withdrawn, or Data Released, it indicates that the request has been resolved, and there will be no further updates regarding that specific request. If one of your requests has been denied or discontinued but you still wish to access the dataset, you can navigate to the record view page and submit a new data access request again.

Note that all the entries in the "my submitted data requests" section will be kept and the delete option is not available.

For more information about the request access workflow, see: [Data Access Process](#)

How to view a Health Dataset in HeSANDA

Record view page overview

Once you have discovered health datasets of interest, the Health Data Australia (HDA) portal provides a comprehensive overview of each dataset's metadata, providing essential information about the dataset and the access option. You can also save the health dataset to your MyHDA profile page, which gives you quick access to this dataset in the future.

One of the prominent features of the record view page is the ability to examine the dataset's connections to other entities. By navigating through the graph visualisation and the listed related parties, you can get a clear understanding about the origin and sourcing of the health dataset, i.e. the funder and the collector. The related study section provided additional details about the study to which the dataset is related. This information expands the scope of understanding by providing valuable context and background information about the dataset.

The figure below shows an example of a record view page in HDA and the name of different sections on the page

Fig 1.1 Record View Page in HDA

Title Bar

The title bar on the record view page presents the most essential information about the health dataset. It includes the dataset's title and the name of its publisher, allowing users to quickly identify and understand the dataset they are reviewing. An icon in the top-right corner specifically indicates the record type.

Data Access and Saving Options

This section provides you with intuitive functionality to interact with your desired datasets. Clicking the button "Access the data" will redirect you to an Express of Interest (EOI) form, in which you can fill in detailed information about yourself and the project you're working on, in order to be granted approval to access the health dataset.

Clicking the button "Save to MyHDA" allows you to save the dataset to MyHDA profile page, so that you can quickly retrieve the dataset for future reference and analysis.

For a more detailed instruction about how to request access to a health dataset, see: [How to Request Access to a Health Dataset](#)

For more information about the saved datasets, see: [MyHDA > My Saved Data Requests](#)

Dataset Description

The Dataset Description section serves as a reference point that provides an overview of the health dataset.

Graph Visualisation

The interactive Graph Visualisation section offers intuitive functionalities for you to explore different connections associated to the health dataset. This powerful feature allows you to uncover relationships with various individuals, organisations, and other health datasets on multiple levels. Different vertices represent different type of entities. The arrows between these vertices indicates the way they are related. You can also double-click any vertex on the graph to see if it's connected with other vertices, so that you can have a more comprehensive view about how data and people/organisations are connected.

For a more detailed instruction about how to use the graph visualisation, see: [Graph Visualisation](#)

Related Parties

This section introduces the individuals and organisations that are related to the current health dataset in text format. For more information about the related parties, see: [Related Parties](#)

Subjects

Each subject in the dataset represents a descriptive element that highlights the primary focus of the health dataset. It aids in the discoverability of datasets and facilitates searching, filtering, and categorisation of datasets that align with your research interests or information requirements. Clicking a subject will redirect you to a search result page displaying all the datasets associated with that subject in their metadata. This allows for convenient exploration and enhances your ability to find relevant and valuable information for your own research needs.

Identifiers

The Identifiers section lists all the available identifiers of the current health dataset and will provide redirection to the identifier if the identifier is resolvable.

Related Study

In HDA, every health dataset is related to a study. This section serves as a valuable resource for understanding the context, background, and additional information related to the dataset's associated study. For more information about the related study, see: [Related Study](#)

Graph Visualisation of a Health Dataset in HeSANDA (requestor)

This documentation explains the types of vertices on an HDA graph visualisation and all the functionalities that it provides.

Overview

The example below shows a typical graph visualisation in the HDA portal, showcasing various types of vertices interconnected through specific relationships. The dataset that's currently being viewed is highlighted for easy identification. At the top-right side of the visualisation, you'll find multiple operational buttons to interact with. To explore the graph further, you can double-click on any vertex or hover your cursor over them. This documentation provides an introduction to the different types of vertices, the information accessible through the graph, and various methods to interact with it.

Fig 2.1 An example of the graph visualisation

Types of vertices

Vertex	Description
	A health dataset
	A Person
	An Organisation/institution or group of people.
	A Publication A publication vertex usually refers to the study related to a given health dataset.

	<p>Primary vertex. This is the vertex representing the health dataset being viewed in Health Data Australia. It is highlighted with a grey ring around it.</p>
	<p>A Cluster. Clusters are an aggregation of single vertices. A cluster is created when there are more than 20 single vertices of the same type with the same relationship to a given vertex. The count of vertices in the cluster is shown on the icon.</p>

Note: Vertices can represent objects which do not exist as a record in Health Data Australia e.g. a publication vertex representing a related study

Expand and collapse the graph visualisation

By default, the graph visualisation is collapsed for a more concise page view. To expand the graph visualisation, simply hover the cursor on the graph visualisation section, and you will see a pop-out message saying "Click to explore relationships graph". Your cursor will also transform into a hand shape. By clicking anywhere on the graph, it will expand to display the vertices and relationships.

Fig 2.2 The pop-out message on the graph visualisation

To collapse the graph visualisation, simply click the round orange button with a bi-directional arrow at the bottom-right corner.

Repositioning the graph

To reposition the graph to any desired position:

- Click and hold your left mouse button down on any white area of the graph canvas.
- Drag the canvas to the desired position.
- Release the left mouse button.

you can also click the Fit-to-Window button to centre the entire graph and ensure that it fits perfectly within the window.

To remove all the changes and reset the graph, click the Reset button.

Zooming in & out

If you have a mouse with a scroll wheel, you can use it to zoom the graph view in and out. The graph will zoom in and out from the location of the mouse pointer, allowing you to zoom into specific parts of the graph by positioning your pointer over the area of interest and then scrolling.

If you don't have a mouse with a scroll wheel, you can still zoom the graph view in and out using the zoom buttons. Use this method in combination with the 'Repositioning the graph' instructions to achieve the desired view.

Highlight a vertex's relationships

To highlight a vertex's relationships, simply hover your mouse pointer over the vertex. This will grey out any vertices which are not directly related.

Fig 2.3 The highlighted relationships of the primary vertex

Expanding a vertex's relationships

Single non-primary vertices often have relationships to vertices that are not directly related to the primary vertex (the record being viewed in Health Data Australia) and are therefore not initially displayed in the graph view. To load additional relationships, double-click on a single vertex. A processing icon will be displayed while the system attempts to load any additional relationships. If no relationships exist for the clicked vertex the current graph view will simply refresh.

Viewing the type and title of a single vertex

To view a vertex's type and title, hover your cursor over the vertex. This action will trigger a tooltip displaying the respective values. Where a health dataset exists in Health Data Australia, the title of the vertex will be displayed as a hyperlink. Simply click the link to view the information about the dataset in HDA.

Fig 2.4 The tooltip for a health dataset vertex

The tooltip for the related study vertex also includes a hyperlink. The difference is that clicking on this link will redirect you to an external page outside of HDA, where you can view detailed information about the study.

For other types of related objects in the graph, such as person and organisation record types, only the name of the record will be shown in the tooltip.

Fig 2.5 The tooltip for an organisation vertex

Viewing the relationships between vertices

To view the relationships between 2 vertices, hover your mouse pointer over the connector. This will display a tooltip with the relationships.

If the text on the connector says "multiple," it indicates that the two vertices are linked through more than one relation. An example is provided below to illustrate the relationships between an organisation and a dataset. In this case, the dataset is both funded by and available through the organisation it points to.

Fig 2.6 The relationships between an organisation and a dataset

How to Request Access to a Health Dataset – HeSANDA

This document serves as a guide to provide an overview of the steps involved in submitting a request, the essential information required in the Expression of Interest (EOI) form, and instructions on how to monitor the status and receive updates regarding your request.

Overview

Once you have browsed the health dataset of your interests and wish to utilise it for your own research project, you can initiate a request for access through Health Data Australia (HDA) by filling in an Express of Interest (EOI) form after logging in with your AAF credentials. HDA offers a streamlined and user-friendly process for requesting access to all the health datasets available. Upon submitting your request, you will receive automated email notifications to keep you informed of any updates regarding your request. Additionally, you can conveniently track the progress and status of your request by accessing your MyHDA profile page.

Overview of the data request process

To make accessing data easier, all datasets listed on HDA adhere to a common framework for responding to data requests.

Figure 1.1 Framework for responding to data requests

Different datasets listed on HDA have different governance and requirements for how access is granted. This information should be included in the listing of each dataset. Some datasets may only be available to certain kinds of researchers or for certain purposes. There may be other conditions for using data such as how it is stored or requirements for collaboration. This information should be included in the listing of each dataset. In most cases, the owner will require a data sharing agreement to be completed before access is granted.

Request Access

To initiate the process of accessing a health dataset in HDA, you need to log in using your AAF credentials first. Once logged in successfully, simply navigate to the record view page of the desired dataset and click the "Access the data" button.

Fig 1.1 The "Access the data" button on the record view page

If you haven't logged in to the HDA portal prior to the request, you'll be redirected to the Keycloak authentication page to proceed.

Express of Interest (EOI) Form

After clicking the "Access the data" button, you should be redirected to a form with multiple tabs. Each tab contains a list of requested information for you to provide. The mandatory fields have a red asterisk (*) next to their names.

Auto-filled Fields

In the EOI form, certain fields will be automatically filled to enhance user experience and minimize manual input errors. These fields include:

- Dataset DOI: the DOI of the health dataset you request access to
- Dataset title: the title of the health dataset you request access to
- Researcher name: Your name as included in the AAF credential
- Email: Your email address as included in the AAF credential

Dataset Requested	Applicant Details	Project Administration	Project Design	Project Outputs	Ethics
Dataset DOI*	http://doi.org/10.25957/P8VP-Y047				
Dataset Title*	Piloting a Treatment to Address Social Media Use and Eating Disorder Risk in University Students				
Data Access Requirement*	Please describe why you require access to the dataset				
Bio Sample:	Please describe any biological sample you require access to.				

Save Next

Fig 2.1 The dataset information has been automatically filled

In addition to these fields, you must complete all the required fields to submit your data access request. To assist you in providing accurate information, tooltips on the right-hand side of each textbox offer detailed explanations of each field. To learn more about each field, simply hover your cursor over the corresponding tooltip.

Fig 2.2 The tooltip and the supportive information it provides

Upload a File

In the last tab of an EOI form, if you selected "Yes" for the first entry: "Do you have ethics approval?" You will need to upload your ethics approval for your project. Click "Choose file" to select and upload the appropriate document.

Please note that the file size must not exceed 10MB, as any file larger than this will fail to upload.

Submit a Data Access Request

After completing all the required fields, you can tick the two checkboxes for the certification and submit your data access request. Clicking "Submit" should successfully submit your request and redirect you to a page displaying all the information provided in the EOI form.

At the top of the page, you will find a notification informing you to track the status and updates of your request through MyHDA:

You have successfully submitted your request to access [redacted] with the following information.
 You can continue to monitor the status of this request through your [MYHDA](#).

Fig 3.1 An example of a successful submission

For instructions about how to monitor the status and updates for a submitted data access request, please refer to:

<https://ardc-datarequest.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/HDA/pages/96862243/MyHDA#My-Submitted-Data-Requests>

Email Notification

After the successful submission, you will receive an email confirming the receipt of your data access request. Subsequent notifications will be sent whenever there are updates. An example email is provided below:

- Request ID: HDA-001
- Status: Submitted
- Dataset name: The title of the requested dataset
- DOI: http://doi.org/10.80298/TEST_DOI_001
- Hello {your email address},
- Thank you for submitting the above data request. The appropriate contacts have been notified and you will receive an update once the review of your request has commenced.
- Issue number assigned to your request: HDA-001.
- Please login to [MyHDA](#) to track the status of your request.
- Please do not reply to this email. Thank you.

Trouble Shooting

Failed to Submit a Request

If any required field is empty or has an invalid value, the submission will fail and error messages will pop out below the buttons on the EOI form, indicating the reason(s) for the failure.

Additionally, a red warning sign will be displayed on each tab that contains missing or invalid fields. When navigating to the respective tab, you will find detailed error messages below each field.

The screenshot shows a multi-tabbed form interface. The tabs are: Dataset Requested, Applicant Details (with a red warning triangle icon), Project Administration, Project Design, Project Outputs, and Ethics. The 'Applicant Details' tab is active. The form contains several questions with radio buttons and checkboxes. Below the questions are three buttons: Previous, Save, and Submit. A red-bordered box highlights the error message 'Invalid ORCID format' located below the buttons.

Fig 3.2 The warning sign on the tab and the error message under the buttons

A close-up of the 'ORCID ID:*' field. The input contains '1111-11110'. Below the field, the error message 'Invalid ORCID format' is displayed in red text.

Fig 3.3 The detailed error message under every missing/invalid field

Didn't Receive Any Email Notification

Troubleshooting email notification issues can be challenging as the notification's behaviour varies depending on the mailbox. If you have not received any email notifications in your inbox, we recommend the following steps:

- Double-check that the email information provided in your AAF credentials is correct.
- Check your "Spam" or "Junk" folder for any misplaced emails.
- If the issue persists, please contact: hesanda@ardc.edu.au or assistance.

When an Active Request Exists

Please note that you won't be able to raise a new data access request if you have raised a request previously AND the request hasn't been resolved. Clicking the "Access the data" button will trigger the following message to be displayed:

Open data access request exists.

You have an open request for access to this data.

Please go to your [MyHDA](#) to monitor this access request.

Fig 3.4 The notification about an existing open data access request

You can click the link to MyHDA to review the existing active request for this dataset.

Save a Data Access Request

Given that completing an EOI form can be a time-consuming process, HDA offers the option to save an unfinished data access request for later. By clicking the "Save" button, you can preserve any changes you want to keep.

To continue editing the EOI form, simply access the "My Saved Data Requests" section on your MyHDA profile page. For more detailed instructions on how to manage your saved requests, See: <https://ardc-datarequest.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/HDA/pages/96862243/MyHDA#My-Saved-Data-Requests>

When an EOI form has been saved to MyHDA, any uploaded files will be associated with the form. You can remove an uploaded file by clicking the delete button next to its name.